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If it was Going to Work it Would Have Worked by Now

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Abstract

A top-down model of educational change and improvement has dominated the landscape of vocational education in England for over 30 years. However, as yet, as Coffield (2017) notes, this model has done little to improve the quality of education or increase learners' achievement across the sector. A reason for this, he argues, is that policy professionals, education leaders and teachers in England have become caught in the grip of a top-down model of educational change and improvement which is proving difficult to loosen. Carr (2005) and Kemmis (2005) contend that a consequence of this is that educational change and improvement in England are now locked in a system which is preoccupied with technique and caught up in a clockwork universe where strategies for the implementation and evaluation of educational policy are coupled with the instrumental language of “recipes” and “blueprints” for “excellent” teaching to command, inhibit and distort the discourse. This paper lends support to the work of the above authors where they argue that these factors make it difficult to see how the education system in England and the model of educational change and improvement which underpins it, could operate in any way other than it currently does. A further consequence of the grip of current model is that quality (what we take to mean by good vocational education) is being reduced to blunt measures of performance outputs imposed from the top-down and measured from the outside-in, which are subsequently presented to the public in the form of competitive league tables (Sennett, 2009). If we accept that we need to rethink existing models of educational change and improvement in vocational education in England, then we need to begin the question of ...where do we start? Drawing attention to the deficiencies of the current model of educational change and improvement is simply not enough. Instead, this paper attempts to make a persuasive case for the need to move towards a new model by providing practical examples which offer glimpses (albeit in microcosm) of how we might go about educational change and improvement differently in the future.

Keywords

models of educational change and improvement, education policy, practitioner-research, vocational education

1 Why vocational education needs a new model of change and improvement

The research problem which provides the central focus of this paper, is that, top-down, models of educational change and improvement in Vocational Education in England which have dominated the landscape for over 30 years, have done little to improve the quality of education

across the sector (Coffield, 2017). A reason for this, Coffield argues, is that policy professionals, education leaders and teachers in England have become caught in the grip of a top-down model of educational change and improvement which is proving difficult to loosen. Carr (2005) and Kemmis (2005) contend that a consequence of this is that educational change and improvement in England are now locked in a system which is preoccupied with technique, where clockwork strategies for the implementation and evaluation of educational policy coupled with the instrumental language of “recipes” and “blueprints” for “excellent” teaching, command and distort the discourse. The above authors argue, these factors make it difficult to see how the education system in England and the model of educational change and improvement which underpins it, could operate in any way other than it currently does. A further consequence of the current model is that quality (what we take to mean by good vocational education) is being reduced to blunt measures of performance outputs imposed from the top-down and measured from the outside-in, which are subsequently presented to the public in the form of competitive league tables (Sennett, 2009). If we accept that we need to rethink existing models of educational change and improvement in vocational education in England, then we need to begin the question of ...where do we start?

Both Carr (2005) and Kemmis (2005) make the point that imposing educational change and improvement from the top-down does not and cannot work because the model itself is founded upon an incoherent, epistemic misconception, premised on a profound misunderstanding of the nature of educational practice (or indeed any practice) and how practice improves. In this paper, we draw upon contributions from the disciplines of philosophy, sociology and psychology through the works of, Sarason (1993), Elliott (2001) Carr (2005), Kemmis (2005), Sennett (2009) and Coffield (2017) among others, to suggest that a first step in this process of moving toward a more pragmatic, inclusive and democratic model of educational change, is to build it upon what we already know about how we as human beings (students, educators, educational researchers, inspectors, policy professionals, as well as whole systems) learn best, namely in mutual collaboration and cooperation. Coffield (2017) draws attention to the paradoxical expectation that a ‘top-down’ model of educational change and improvement that, creates a climate of fear, relies upon fabrications of reality and truth and assumes that teachers and educational leaders will somehow be inspired to improve what they do in the face of the threat of public humiliation, will “work” in practice is quite absurd. Such categorial flaws and misconceptions, based upon the relatively recent and arbitrary separation of concepts of, theory, practice and research, as well as binary framings of vocational and academic education, when combined with assumptions about the temporal relationship between theory and practice, have also led to impractical divisions of labour and unhelpful demarcations of practice in educational research. These are regularly framed in highly questionable and demeaning hierarchical terms, which elevate ‘academic’ education above ‘vocational’ education. Such dislocations and false, hierarchical, epistemic constructions have not only come to frame how we think and talk about systematic and impactful educational research, but also who is best placed to legitimately conduct it. The same exclusionary forces have also served to relegate and reduce technological and vocational education to simple matters of technique, rote learning and mindless rule-following. This has culminated in a diminished understanding of what constitutes the genuine development and improvement of different forms of knowledge, skill and craft in the world. At the same time, this discourse has also served to obscure what it means to lead a fulfilled life and be a well-educated human being today.

On the other side of the Atlantic, but from a similar perspective, Sarason (1998) invites us to consider,

Why ...have our efforts – and they were many and expensive – met with intractability? Why should we expect that what we will now recommend will be any more effective than our past efforts?

Sarason, 1998, p.3.

This paper aims to address the research question of what an alternative, more democratic and inclusive model of educational change and improvement might look like in practice in vocational education contexts? The parameters of this research are set in the context of the Practitioner Research Programme (PRP), a national programme of intensive educational research training, internship and mentoring for teachers working the Further Adult Vocational and Technological Education (FAVTE) sector in England. Funded by the Education and Training Foundation (ETF) for over 7 years, the PRP, provides intensive research training, support and internship for teachers and education leaders working in the FAVTE sector.

To date, over 350 sector practitioners across England have successfully engaged and subsequently graduated from the PRP at either, Master of Arts (MA), Master of Philosophy (MPhil) or Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degree level. The methodological position or logic framing the research is inductive, beginning with particular cases, we illustrate the lived experiences of PRP participants working across a range of different vocational subjects and disciplines as they learn how to be (*savoir être*), credible, respected peer-reviewed, educational researchers in their own right, conducting research into an aspect of their own practice and how it might be improved. From the PRP research population of 350, extracts from a small sample of cases and evaluative commentaries from PRP participants working in 2 colleges of Further Education (FE) and one Industry Training Provider are employed for illustrative purposes. Thematic analysis of these cases (Nowell et al 2017) is then put to work to offer some practical examples of and insights into what an alternative model of educational change and improvement might look like in action.

The theoretical framework employed in this study draws upon Dewey's (1910, 1933) pragmatic epistemology and works of Dunne (1997, 2005) among others, to draw attention to the importance of context in educational change and improvement. The same framework also foregrounds the role of Aristotle's (384-322 BC) different forms of knowledge in the development and improvement of practice in vocational education contexts. Our aim is to bring the reasons why teachers often encounter problems in putting theories and ideas from research conducted by others into practice into view. We employ Dunne's (2005) definition of practice research to explain why an appreciation of the different forms of knowledge embedded and embodied in experience and practice are pivotal in the success of models of educational change and improvement in Vocational Education. Dunne defines, a practice as,

“ ... a coherent and invariably quite complex set of activities and tasks that has evolved cooperatively and cumulatively over time. It is alive in the community who are its insiders (i.e. its genuine practitioners) and it stays alive only so long as they sustain a commitment to creatively develop and extend it – sometimes by shifts which may at the time seem dramatic or even subversive. Central to any such practice are standards of excellence, themselves subject to development and redefinition, which demand responsiveness from those who are, or are trying to become practitioners”

Dunne 2005, pp. 152-153.

Note how Dunne draws our attention to historical, incremental, social and cultural dimensions of a practice and the processes through which practice is evolved by its insiders, in the contexts

and sites in which their practice is conducted. From here we can see that research in Further, Adult, Vocational and Technological Education (FAVTE) contexts is neither a new, nor an inferior way of thinking about educational change and improvement. We extend Dunne's (1995) definition of a practice into the work of Sennett (2009), where he argues that all skills, even the most abstract, begin as bodily practices and that technical understanding develops, not in a mechanical or mindless way but through the acquisition and development of different forms of knowledge including problem-finding, problem-solving and critique, as well through the powers of imagination and aesthetic experience (Sennett, 2009). From this perspective, ideas about what makes a practice good in any form of life, originate in our experiences of trying to do something well in the world, making critical judgements regarding the consequences of our actions in practice and deciding how we might do better in the future. Reaching back into the history of human experience of thinking through making, practice research focuses on the importance of dialogue between concrete practices, thinking, problem-finding, problem-solving and critique (Sennett, 2009).

Embodied in the world, practice research conducted in the PRP has real and direct consequences for learners, teachers, communities, the economy and society. Practice research in the PRP admits and values different forms of knowledge and understanding in ways which include, practical and material experience (thinking through making); the exercise of practical wisdom in context; the development of theory alongside the development of qualities of mind and character. Such qualities include, an ability for independent thought and reflection; a care for clarity and expressiveness in writing and speech; a habit of truthfulness; a commitment to open mindedness; a disposition towards cooperation and collaboration; a sense of justice; the courage to move beyond the narrow pursuit of self-interest and a genuine commitment to act publicly in the pursuit of the common good (Dunne 1997, p.6). These distinctive human qualities operate to signal what we mean when we talk about good education in FAVTE contexts as preparation and support for, the development and nurturing of good practice and human flourishing in any form of life. Such qualities of mind and character resonate closely with VETNET ambitions to educate and prepare learners in FAVTE to the highest level, to enable them to be work-ready, lifelong learners with an international outlook and the knowledge and skills necessary to navigate the global workplace as well as making a contribution to global citizenship and the common good.

This paper, the problems which it addresses and the themes and findings drawn from PRP data are reported here to illuminate the need to move away from current preoccupations with technique and mechanical and arbitrary separations of theory, practice and research in programmes for the initial and continuing professional development of teachers in FAVTE. We argue that a move toward approaches to curriculum design and pedagogic practices, informed by social, collaborative, cooperative and aesthetic experiences which evoke the development of the person within the teacher is long overdue. Data from the PRP reported below indicate how practice research together with the expressive qualities of the arts can be put to work in developing the minds, imagination and character of vocational teachers and learners alike. It is hoped that the findings described in this paper may be of interest and use to teachers and teacher-educators in vocational, further and higher education, policy professionals, curriculum developers and those with responsibility for educational evaluation and improvement in the FAVTE sector and in other sectors of education.

2 Findings

1. Prior to the PRP practitioners in the FAVTE sector were routinely assumed to be poorly informed about practice even though they know it 'from the inside'. On the other hand, university researchers, academics and theorists were regarded as being well informed about practice even though they are largely removed from it by the day-to-day division of labour

(Kemmis, 2005). These issues are particularly important in relation to the impact (or otherwise) of educational research upon educational practice in vocational education in the real world. The PRP is helping teachers to make informed judgements based on an appropriate balance of evidence framed by a new infrastructure or “information architecture” (Goldacre 2010) capable of supporting the more democratic, inclusive and realistic approaches to the improvement of educational practice.

2. The PRP provides examples of how practitioner-research can go beyond ‘big research’ to bring to life the people behind the numbers by offering insights into *how* and *why* an idea or theory from educational research which claims *that* something has ‘worked’ (in an experiment, randomised control or other research trial) actually ‘works’ or ‘fails’ to work in practice. The PRP begins with questions of practice that matter to practitioners, the real world concerns of teachers regarding problems they encounter in educational practice. This means that at least some of the evidence generated in the PRP research process is derived from the first-hand experiences of sector practitioners. This makes PRP research of relevance, interest and most importantly of use to practitioners. In turn, this makes its impact upon educational practice, direct, context-attuned and more immediate in ways which other forms of research can find problematic. Research conducted in and through the PRP, employs a blend of research evidence generated by sector practitioners and by others in the educational research community. This blend of research evidence contributes to the accessibility and credibility of PRP research as it connects and resonates with the lived experiences of teachers and is used by and is useful to them and their colleagues in ways which both challenge, support and extend educational research conducted by others.

3. The PRP is contributing to making the critical and thoughtful use of evidence from research a part of the everyday practice of teachers by providing intensive research training and internship for teachers as an integral part of their continuing professional development (CPD) equipping “the researched” with the knowledge and skills they need to become respected, credible and in some cases published researchers. In the PRP practitioners develop an understanding of what is meant by ‘good research’ in education and how good research is and is not done. This is enabling teachers across the sector to become not only critical readers, writers and ‘testers’ of the findings of research conducted by others but also enabling them to become developers and critics of their own research. The PRP is building the self-improving capacity of the sector by providing intensive research training which supports the development of highly skilled, practice-focused, systematic, rigorous and impactful practitioner-research. The PRP is driving sector-wide improvement in context through a pioneering model of educational change which enables practitioners in the FE sector to test out and adapt ideas from educational theory and research in the arena of practice.

4. By providing detailed ‘on the ground’ descriptions of what goes on in practice through direct accounts of the lived experiences of teachers, education leaders and learners, the PRP provides cumulative, real-world and real-time insights into the *processes* through which a policy or idea from research is being implemented in practice *as* it is being implemented. This offers policy professionals a ‘history of the present’, intelligence in the ‘here and now’, insights into what is really happening to an idea from research/policy in practice. This presents opportunities to adapt, modify and improve policy in practice in real-time in the light of incrementally accrued evidence, derived from the direct experiences of sector practitioners, including more subtle and less easily measured aspects of the (lived) impact of an idea from research or a policy in practice. Research conducted in the PRP is distinct from much ‘rear view mirror’ sector intelligence generated by RCTs, meta-analyses and other forms of ‘big research’ which present retrospective perspectives of the large-scale outcomes and more easily measured aspects of the impact of a policy, after the event and from the outside. This is not to say that the PRP and ‘big research’ conducted through RCTs should be viewed in binary or oppositional

terms or that one should be elevated or valued above the other. The PRP offers a new model of partnership in which practitioner research can contribute to/supplement ‘big’ research in the form of RCTs in a complementary and mutually enriching relationship capable of improving and informing both forms of research in education. In this way, the PRP offers opportunities to develop a new, more inclusive and democratic architecture for a hybrid model of policy-research-practice relations, a new policy science capable of harnessing synergies derived from both forms of educational research opening up opportunities for hypothesis-testing on a smaller scale *before/after* hypothesis-testing on a larger scale through RCTs etc. An aim of the PRP is to challenge ideas about what counts as systematic research in education in the FAVTE sector, regarding how research is conducted, who gets to conduct it and who can legitimately talk about the experiences of ‘the researched’. A central question here is what happens to educational research when ‘the researched’ become the researchers? The PRP takes research to be an educative process, where the first objective is to illuminate and explore educational problems and enduring educational issues encountered by teachers in their everyday practice and to pursue potential solutions through practitioner-research.

5. In the top-down model practitioner research and the people who conduct it are subordinated, undervalued, overlooked and largely excluded from the educational research community. The PRP is challenging unhelpful binary debates and discourses surrounding the importance and value of practitioner-research *versus* ‘big research’ increasing knowledge and improving educational policy-research-practice relations in education in the process. A further objective of the PRP is to contest previously uncritically accepted relays of power and dominant relations of authority which elevate ‘big’ research (RCTs, meta analyses and other forms of research) which conduct research *on* education from the top-down and from the outside-in), and elevate its worth to be above that of practitioner-research, considering it to be superior to and more useful.

6. Through the PRP, highly experienced and more mature teachers and education leaders across the FAVTE sector in England now have access to intensive training and internship in educational research, scholarship and academic writing. This is beginning to contribute to greater inclusion and to use a phrase currently in vogue a “levelling up” of the current demography of the educational research community in which more mature teacher-researchers from lower socio-economic groups who were previously excluded and under-represented in the educational research community and in the academy, can now participate in and contribute to research, theory and knowledge development, the improvement of educational practice in education and in doing so strengthen social justice in the academic and research community.

3 Conclusion

Data from the PRP suggest that if the top-down model of educational change and improvement was going to work it would have worked by now. Data also indicate that HE-supported practitioner-research in vocational education contexts such as that embodied in the PRP offer an important, powerful and useful engine for the refinement of international models of educational change and the improvement in FAVTE contexts, from the ground-up.

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Biographical note

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